

S I N G L E

D8.1 Establish the web-based shared information space

WP8, T8.1

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Technical references

PROJECT INFORMATION

Project Acronym	SINGLE
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DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Deliverable No.	D8.1
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Task	T8.1 - Project management and coordination
Lead beneficiary	1 (CTMS)
Contributing beneficiary/ies	2(CSIC), 3(GECRIO), 4(UL), 5(SINTEF), 6(ICONS), 7(UPC)
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* PU = Public, SEN = Sensitive, EU classified = RESTREINT-UE/EU-RESTRICTED, CONFIDENTIEL-UE/EU-CONFIDENTIAL, SECRET-UE/EU-SECRET under Decision 2015/444

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Executive summary

In the present public document, we share the elements that are on the SINGLE SharePoint site, a web-based shared information space for all project partners.

DOCUMENT HISTORY:

v	Date	Author(s)	Description
0.9	23/08/2023	Selene Hernández Morejudo (CTMS)	First draft to partners
1.0	28/08/2023	Selene Hernández Morejudo (CTMS)	Final version

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1. Introduction

SINGLE SharePoint is a web-based share information site designed to serve as an internal home page for SINGLE project where all project partners can share project updates and access SINGLE project documents. SINGLE SharePoint is a private site and only partners can access the site and site contents. The site was fully operational in M1 (May 2023).

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2. SINGLE SharePoint

SINGLE SharePoint content (Figure 1):

1. Documents - Easy and secure access to project files
2. Progress tracker list - Keep track of all tasks related to SINGLE project (Figure 2)
3. Deliverables tracker list - Track all deliverables of SINGLE project (Figure 3)
4. Events - Displays the next events, as on-line or in-person meetings
5. Project contacts – Direct access to SINGLE project coordinators

The screenshot displays the SINGLE SharePoint interface. The top navigation bar includes the SharePoint logo, a search bar, and the site name 'SINGLE - 10112144'. The left sidebar contains navigation options: Home, Documents, Notebook, Calendar, Progress tracker list, Deliverable tracker list, Recycle bin, and Edit. The main content area is divided into several sections:

- Documents (1):** A table listing project files:

Name	Modified	Modified By
1. Administrative	May 16	Selene Hernandez-Morej...
2. Project description	May 16	Selene Hernandez-Morej...
3. WPs	May 16	Selene Hernandez-Morej...
4. Deliverables	May 16	Selene Hernandez-Morej...
5. Meetings	May 16	Selene Hernandez-Morej...
- Activity:** A list of recent activities, including 'D&I v1' edited 3 minutes ago and 'D7' edited 4 hours ago.
- Team tools:** Includes 'SINGLE_Gantt project planner' and 'Whiteboard'.
- Events (4):** A section for adding and viewing events, with a 'Create an event' button and a list of events for the current month.
- Project contacts (5):** A list of team members with their initials and names: Selene Hernandez-Morejudo, Ruth Moya (GECRIO), Harald Materød-Fjeld, and Christian Kjøseth.

Figure 1: SINGLE SharePoint

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The screenshot shows a SharePoint 'Progress tracker list' for a private group named 'SINGLE - 10112144'. The list contains 16 tasks, each with a unique ID, a Work Package (WP), a progress status (In progress or Not started), a start date, a due date, a lead, and a list of partners.

Work item	WP	Progress	Start date	Due date	Lead	Partners
Task 1.1. Improvement of the catalytic activit...	WP1	In progress	May 01	October 30, 2024	CSIC	CTMS
Task 1.2. Improvement of the stability of Ni...	WP1	In progress	May 01	October 30, 2024	CTMS	CSIC
Task 1.3. Cell's components compatibility wi...	WP1	In progress	May 01	October 30, 2024	CSIC	CTMS
Task 1.4. Testing of optimized single cells	WP1	Not started	October 01	September 30, 2025	CSIC	CTMS
Task 2.1. Definition of qualification criteria a...	WP2	In progress	May 01	October 31	CTMS	SINTEF, CSIC, UL
Task 2.2. Screening of candidate materials a...	WP2	Not started	October 01	March 31, 2025	SINTEF	CTMS, CSIC
Task 2.3. Validation under realistic operatin...	WP2	Not started	February 01, 2024	July 31, 2025	SINTEF	CTMS
Task 3.1. Fabrication of cells and KET compo...	WP3	In progress	May 01	October 30, 2025	CTMS	CSIC
Task 3.2. Manufacturing of stacks	WP3	Not started	February 01, 2024	April 30, 2026	CTMS	CSIC
Task 3.3. Module manufacturing	WP3	Not started	February 01, 2025	April 30, 2026	CTMS	CSIC, UPC
Task 3.4. Validation of stack components	WP3	Not started	Today	January 31, 2025	CSIC	CTMS
Task 3.5. Performance and long-term testin...	WP3	Not started	October 01	November 30, 2025	CSIC	CTMS
Task 4.1. Modelling of cells and stacks and s...	WP4	In progress	May 01	April 30, 2026	CTMS	CSIC, UPC
Task 4.2. Safety assessment and operation p...	WP4	Not started	October 01, 2024	April 30, 2026	CSIC	SINTEF, UPC, GECRIO
Task 4.3. Advanced process control	WP4	Not started	May 01, 2024	April 30, 2026	UPC	CSIC, CTMS

Figure 2: Progress tracker list.

The screenshot shows a SharePoint 'Deliverables tracker list' for the same private group. The list contains 16 deliverables, each with a unique ID, a lead, a Work Package (WP), a status (In progress or Not started), a due date, associated files, and a date delivered.

Deliverable	Lead	WP	Status	Due date	Associated files	Date delivered
D1.1 Report on development on Ni/BZCY c...	CSIC	WP1	Not started	January 31, 2024		
D1.2 Final report on catalytic performance ...	CSIC	WP1	Not started	October 31, 2024		
D1.3 Results on single-tube testing for am...	CSIC	WP1	Not started	April 30, 2025		
D2.1 Definition of qualification criteria for s...	CTMS	WP2	In progress	5 days from now		
D2.2 Definition of test protocols for screeni...	SINTEF	WP2	Not started	October 31		
D2.3 List of candidate alloys to be included ...	SINTEF	WP2	Not started	October 31		
D2.4 Report on materials durability in relev...	SINTEF	WP2	Not started	June 30, 2024		
D2.5 Report on materials validation and rec...	CTMS	WP2	Not started	October 31, 2024		
D3.1 Cells and KET components fabrication ...	CTMS	WP3	Not started	October 31		
D3.2 Cells and KET components fabrication ...	CTMS	WP3	Not started	October 31, 2024		
D3.3 Stack delivery	CTMS	WP3	Not started	October 31		
D3.4 Module delivery	CTMS	WP3	Not started	October 31, 2025		
D3.5 Consolidated report on stack compon...	CTMS	WP3	Not started	October 31, 2024		
D3.6 Final report on the performance and d...	CSIC	WP3	Not started	June 30, 2025		

Figure 3: Deliverables tracker list.

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